

RARE BIRDS ENTERED IN THE "RED BOOK" IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article discusses the life of birds in Uzbekistan, which are included in the "Red Book". The Republic of Uzbekistan is famous for its natural resources, including rare and endangered bird species. Birds play an important role not only in maintaining the stability of the ecosystem, but also in combating pests in agriculture. Unfortunately, due to human activity and changes in the natural environment, many bird species are under threat of extinction. Therefore, the government of Uzbekistan has included some of them in the "Red Book".

Key words: "Red Book", the threat of extinction, bird conservation, diversity, rare birds, white stork, black stork, tawny eagle, falcon, jay crane, swan, velvet pheasant, bird conservation, anti-poaching law, environmental education, biosphere reserve.

O'ZBEKISTONDA "QIZIL KITOB"GA KIRITILGAN NOYOB QUSHLAR.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistonda "Qizil kitob"ga kiritilgan qushlar hayoti yoritiladi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi tabiiy boyliklari, jumladan, noyob va yo'qolib borayotgan qush turlari bilan mashhur. Qushlar nafaqat ekotizim barqarorligini saqlashga, balki qishloq xo'jaligida zararkunandalarga qarshi kurashda ham muhim rol o'ynaydi. Afsuski, inson faoliyati va tabiiy muhitning o'zgarishi tufayli ko'plab qush turlari yo'qolib ketish xavfi ostida qolgan. Shu sababli, O'zbekiston hukumati ularning ayrimlarini "Qizil kitob"ga kiritgan.

Kalit so'zlar: "Qizil kitob", yo'qolish xavfi, qushlarni muxofaza qilish, xilma-xillik, noyob qushlar, oq laylak qora laylak, to'qay burguti, lochin, jaydari turna, oqqush, baxmal tuyg'un, qushlarni asrash, brakonerlikka qarshi qonun, ekologik ta'lim, biosfera rezervati.

Introduction: The Red Book of Uzbekistan is an official state document containing an annotated list of the most rare and endangered species of flora and

fauna in the territory of Uzbekistan, as well as generalized information on their distribution. The current state of these species leads to a decrease in the population and measures are being taken to preserve and reproduce them. Plant and animal species included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan are specially protected throughout the republic. The Red Book was first published in Uzbekistan in 1979 and was subsequently republished several times. The last time it included 57 species of birds. An updated Red Book was published in 2019.

Main part: Some rare birds listed in the "Red Book" of Uzbekistan

1. White stork (*Ciconia ciconia*) - The white stork is one of the rarest birds in Uzbekistan. They usually live in river valleys, wetlands and rural areas. The main threats are habitat loss, human activity and a decrease in the food base.

2. Black stork (*Ciconia nigra*) - Very rare in Uzbekistan. Lives in mountainous areas and forested areas. The main threat is deforestation and human disturbance.

3. Bald eagle (*Aquila clanga*) - One of the large birds of prey. It lives mainly in the forests along the Amu Darya and Syrdarya rivers and feeds on fish and rodents. It is disappearing due to the destruction of forests along the rivers and hunting.

4. Peregrine Falcon (*Falco peregrinus*) - One of the fastest flying birds in the world. It is mainly found in mountainous areas and desert zones. It is decreasing due to illegal hunting of birds and their removal from the wild.

5. White-crowned Crane (*Grus leucogeranus*) - A very rare bird in Uzbekistan. It lives mainly near agricultural lands and water bodies. Cranes are decreasing due to habitat loss and poaching.

6. Whooper Swan (*Cygnus cygnus*) - Found in Uzbekistan as a wintering bird. Swans live in swamps and water bodies. They are at risk of extinction due to poaching and habitat loss.

7. Eurasian Scops Owl (*Otus tarda*) - One of the largest land-dwelling birds. They are mainly found in forest-steppe and desert areas. The main threat is poaching and the expansion of agricultural activities.

Bird Conservation Measures

The Uzbek government and environmental organizations are taking the following measures to prevent bird extinction:

1. Establishing protected areas (e.g., Saiga Reserve, Jaikhun Biosphere Reserve).

2. Strengthening anti-poaching laws and increasing fines.

3. Restoring and protecting bird habitats, including protecting water bodies.

4. Increasing public interest in bird conservation through increased environmental education and outreach.

Conclusion: Most of the birds listed in the Red Book of Uzbekistan are declining due to human activity and environmental changes. To preserve these unique species, it is very important to expand protected areas, combat poaching, and develop environmental education. If we work on nature conservation, future

generations will also have the opportunity to see these beautiful birds in their natural environment. It is necessary to preserve these birds by preserving their habitat, prohibiting their hunting, and harming nature. Protecting the natural environment and paying attention to environmental problems is the main factor in passing on rare birds and nature in general to future generations in a healthy state.

REFERENCES USED:

- 1-S. Dadayev, Q. Saparov; O‘zR oliy a o‘rta-maxsus ta’lim vazirligi. T.Cho‘lpon nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2011. - 512 b.
- 2- S.Dadayev/O. Mavlonov; O‘zR oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi, Nizomiy nomidagi Toshkent Davlat pedagogika un-ti. TIQTISOD-MOLIYA" 2008, 184 b.
- 3- S. DADAYEV, S. TO‘YCHIEV, P. HAYDAROVA O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti Toshkent — 2006
4. Haqberdiyeva S. T. Improving the Teaching Methods of Biology in General Secondary Schools on the Basis of A Competency-based Approach //Academicia Globe. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 03. – C. 132-136.
5. Tursunaliyevna H. S., Nozima A. Effectiveness of using innovative technologies in teaching the morphology of bacteria //Journal of Universal Science Research. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 10. – C. 60-66.